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Sustainable Industry 4.0

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ABSTRACT

Sustainability and Industry 4.0 have been dominating debates as the most pressing problems and challenges for society in general and for engineering in particular. Industry 4.0 contributes as a vision, where new technology plays a key role in the future. As sustainability is such an urgent issue, it would be expected that the vision of Industry 4.0 would include and address sustainability goals as key targets goals. However, this is not the case or at least it is not explicitly.

This paper discusses Sustainability and Industry 4.0 implications from the perspective of engineering education. The aim is to identify which needs for knowledge and competences these two concepts call for in the future to prepare engineering education. Thus, it is important to examine the relation and emergent opportunities for engineers to contribute to a Sustainable Industry 4.0.

This paper points to two major opportunities to combine Sustainability and Industry 4.0, at technological and at competence levels. Industry 4.0 core technologies enable to integrate sustainability strategies throughout the entire supply chain, through a more efficient use of resources and energy. In addition, the competences needed for Sustainability and Industry 4.0 seem to overlap, especially transversal competences such as: problem solving, communication, creativity, leadership, collaboration and lifelong learning.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sustainability and Industry 4.0 are two trends in engineering, which will irrevocably affect in which ways engineers work and are educated.

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Climate change, resources depletion, environment degradation, inequality and poverty, are some of the problems society is facing. Furthermore, societal and economic progress still relies heavily on technology and innovation. However, technological development has the possibility to provide solutions capable of solving sustainable problems locally and globally. See for example, the United Nations published the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which constitute a framework for sustainable development actions towards 2030. The SDGs are a set of 17 goals and 169 targets, formulated based on previous declarations and the eight Millennium Goals not achieved for Sustainable Development (MGSDs) (2000-2015). The SDGs highlight the role of technology support and achieve the 17 goals and targets [1].

On the other hand, new ideas and technologies from Industry 4.0 will transform the entire structure of work places, world economy, communities and human identities. Technologies such as automation and internet of things (IoT) will drastically affect human, social and economic development, and as consequent, industry has to reconsider their ways of doing business to keep with rapidly technology innovation and consumers expectations [2][3].

In order to face the Sustainability challenges and Industry 4.0 demands, engineering education needs to revise their curriculum, the qualification profiles and pedagogical models. Even though curriculum changes and development of teaching methods have been taking place around the world, the process has been slow and, often, at course and programme levels. Frequently, curriculum change aims to develop the qualification profile and to make students more employable, neglecting the sustainability knowledge and competences [4]. In addition, when sustainability is integrated in engineering education, it is mainly through elective stand-alone courses and programmes, which is not enough [5]. In sum, changes are taking place, but they are still behind the needs, and rarely address both Industry 4.0 and Sustainability. Furthermore, it is claimed that engineering overcrowded curriculum constitutes a barrier for curriculum innovation and change, whereas “*for something to get in, something needs to get out*”. Therefore, it is needed to investigate in which ways Industry 4.0 and Sustainability can be combined and integrated in engineering education by, for example, examining which opportunities exists for combining Sustainability and Industry 4.0. This paper discusses such issue by addressing the following research question through a literature review:

What are the opportunities to combine Sustainability and Industry 4.0?

We start by conceptualizing Industry 4.0 and the competences needed (section 2), followed by the discussion of the opportunities to combine Sustainability within Industry 4.0 context (section 3). We conclude the paper answering the research question (section 4), and briefly discussing the implications for engineering education.

2 INDUSTRY 4.0 CONCEPTUALIZATION

Most of the Industry 4.0 literature relates to the technologies that bring together the concept. In 2015, the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) [6] published a report describing nine technological trends as the building blocks of Industry 4.0. These nine technologies reflect very well the general concept of Industry 4.0. They are:

- Big Data and Analytics
- Autonomous Robots
- Simulation
- Horizontal and Vertical System Integration
- The Industrial Internet of Things
- Cyber Security
- The Cloud
- Additive Manufacturing
- Augmented Reality

Most of these new technologies are already available, although they are mainly used in other types of applications, such as within the consumer industry. However, with Industry 4.0, they will transform production into a fully integrated, automated and optimized production flow. It will lead to an increased efficiency and change traditional production conditions between suppliers, manufacturers and customers, as well as between man and machine. The implementation of Industry 4.0 will not only change the traditional relationships between man and machine, but will also place new demands on employees' competencies. Current expectations fall on employees who will increasingly focus on creative, innovative and communicative activities. Routine activities, such as monitoring tasks, are taken over entirely or partly by machines. The earlier waves of industrialization, however, showed that technological progress did not diminish overall employment rate. Although the number of production workers declined, new jobs emerged and the demand for new skills grew [7]. Today, a new workforce transformation awaits.

Industry 4.0 calls for a new qualification profile and competences. *Table 1* presents three frameworks, which define the expected competences required [8][9][10]. The three frameworks highlight the need for competences related with ICT and digitalization, transversal skills and technical expertise.

Table 1. Competence frameworks for Industry 4.0, according to [8][9][10].

Erol et al. (2016)	Hecklau et al. (2016)	Motyl et al. (2017)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domain competences <p>(e.g. application of, e.g. lean thinking and methods in manufacturing; application conceptual modelling methods, e.g. data flow, material flow)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical competences <p>(e.g. state-of-the-art knowledge; technical skills; process understanding; media skills; coding skills; understanding IT security)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard skills <p>(e.g. numerical and higher mathematical knowledge; problem solving; creativity and design skills; investigative and experimental skills; information</p>

<p>and process modelling; application of information and communication technology (ICT) for material tracking and worker tracking)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action competences <p>(e.g. problem analysis and structuring, solution and development; data analysis and interpretation; method, tool selection and use)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal Competences <p>(e.g. solution-oriented attitude; creativity; out-of-the-box thinking)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social competences <p>(e.g. teamwork ability; consensus-finding ability, compromising; role taking, role-making ability)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodological competences <p>(e.g. creativity; entrepreneurial thinking; problem solving; conflict solving; decision making; analytical skills; research skills; efficiency orientation)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal competences <p>(e.g. flexibility; ambiguity tolerance; motivation to learn; ability to work under pressure; sustainable mind-set; compliance)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social competences <p>(e.g. intercultural skills; language skills; communication skills; networking skills; ability to work in a team; ability to be compromising and cooperative; ability to transfer knowledge; leadership skills)</p>	<p>processing; computer programming; knowledge of specific software tools)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital skills <p>(e.g. basic digital literacy skills, such as use of digital applications and ability to carry out basic internet searches; digital skills for general workforce² such as specific use of IT applications for workplace, developed by IT specialists and processing information; digital skills³ for ICT professionals, such as skills linked to development of new digital technologies, products and services)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soft skills <p>(e.g. strong analytical thinking; communication; teamwork; leadership)</p>
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At first sight, the competences required seem quite generic, however their association and interrelation with digital technologies omen about a radically new job and competence profiles [8][9][10]. Furthermore, the role of employees will change from operators to problem-solvers and companies should make an effort concerning an enhanced interdisciplinary education in the areas of economics, engineering, informatics, and mathematics, with, e.g., educational institutions [11]. It will be necessary to introduce competence strategies and, for example, to organize work in a way that promotes learning, enabling workplace/work-based learning, i.e. lifelong learning.

Undoubtedly, Industry 4.0 arrives with promise to deeply change the industry and work places, which will also affect the way engineers are educated. However, what seems to be unchanged is the incentives (i.e. the driving forces behind) for Industry 4.0, which are still based on the mind-set of the previous waves of industrialisation, i.e. the economic growth and capitalization way of thinking. Even though two of the frameworks presented in *Table 1* refer to sustainability-related competences, such as “lean thinking methods” [8] and “sustainable mind-set” [9], in general Industry 4.0

²Digital skills for general workforce includes basic digital literacy skills.

³Digital skills for ICT professionals includes all skills from basic digital skills and digital skills for general workplace.

does not explicitly state sustainability as a goal. In fact, it seems that sustainability principles are not adapted to Industry 4.0 concept. The next section discusses the opportunities to combine sustainability and Industry 4.0.

3 OPPORTUNITIES FOR COMBINING SUSTAINABILITY AND INDUSTRY 4.0

The increase societal expectations towards decreasing the environmental impacts caused by, for example, manufacturing industry push companies not only to focus on profit and maximization, but also to develop sustainable practices and business models [12]-[15]. Literature shows that sustainability can be combined with Industry 4.0 mainly through its core technologies and the competences needed.

Industry 4.0 core technologies allow transparency in the production and organisational processes, fast in real time exchange/integration of information, which leads to an efficient allocation and use of resources in the management of production and organisational processes [12][14]. For example, intelligent scheduling of tasks and processes, processes simulations, prediction of energy consumption through smart energy systems, can optimize and reduce the energy consumption. In addition, manufacturing design “*can be improved through direct data interconnection from product usage back to design*” [12]. This allows recovering, reusing and recycling components, which decrease the use raw materials and waste, improving the product lifecycle and reducing greenhouse gas emissions [12][13].

Stock & Seliger [14] argue “*Industry 4.0 will be a step forward towards more sustainable industrial value creation*”. The authors refer that the allocation and use of resources will be more efficient by the means of intelligent cross-linked value creation modules, proving opportunities for sustainable manufacturing at organizational, process and product levels. For example, at organizational level, efficient allocation of products, materials, energy and water. At process level, sustainable design by addressing the holistic resource efficiency approach. At product level, realization of close-loop life cycle for products by reusing and remanufacturing of specific products, or by applying cradle-to-cradle principles. Muller et al. [12] and Stock & Seliger [14] relate social sustainability with employees, job market, working environment, qualification and acceptance. They outline several benefits for the employees, namely “*human learning through intelligent assistance systems as well as human machines interfaces that lead to increased employee satisfaction in industrial workplaces*”. Even though there is a concern of job lost due to replacement of human employees by robots or automatic systems, current literature does not provide a unified perspective. However, simple and monotonous tasks are expected to be replaced and new job profiles will be required [14]. Furthermore, Industry 4.0 vision claims to be human-centred where a “*flexible work organization will enable workers to combine their work, private lives, and continuing professional development more effectively, promoting a better work-life balance*” [16].

Sustainability can be define as complex, interdisciplinary, participatory, contextual, problem- and action-oriented. Therefore, addressing sustainable problems calls for competences aligned with sustainability principles and goals. Based on sustainability research and problem-solving frameworks, Wiek et al. [17] identify five key competences in sustainability, which are systems thinking, strategic and interpersonal competences, normative and anticipatory competences (*Table 2*).

Table 2. Competence framework for sustainability (retrieved from Wiek et al. [17])

Competence	Definition	Associated terms and concepts
Systems thinking	Ability to collectively analyse complex systems across different domains (society, environment, economy, etc.) and across different scales (local to global and temporal), thereby considering cascading effects, inertia, feedback loops and other systemic features related to sustainability issues and sustainability problem-solving frameworks.	Systemic thinking, interconnected thinking, holistic thinking, coupled human-environment; systems, social-ecological systems
Anticipatory	Ability to collectively analyse, evaluate, and craft rich “pictures” of the future. The ability to analyse includes being able to comprehend and articulate their structure, key components, and dynamics; the ability to evaluate refers to comparative skills that relate to the “state of the art”; finally, the ability to craft integrates creative and constructive skills.	Anticipatory thinking, future thinking, foresighted thinking, trans-generational thinking
Normative	Normative competence is the ability to collectively map, specify, apply, reconcile, and negotiate sustainability values, principles, goals, and targets. This capacity enables, first, to collectively assess the (un-)sustainability of current and/or future states of social-ecological systems and, second, to collectively create and craft sustainability visions for these systems. This capacity is based on acquired normative knowledge	Value-focused thinking, orientation thinking/knowledge, ethical thinking

	including concepts of justice, equity, social-ecological integrity, and ethics.	
Strategic	Ability to collectively design and implement interventions, transitions, and transformative governance strategies toward sustainability. This capacity requires an intimate understanding of strategic concepts such as intentionality, systemic inertia, path dependencies, barriers, carriers, alliances, etc.; knowledge about viability, feasibility, effectiveness, efficiency of systemic interventions as well as potential of unintended consequences.	Linked closely to normative, anticipatory and systems thinking competences. Action-oriented competence, transformative competence, implementation skills
Interpersonal	Ability to motivate, enable, and facilitate collaborative and participatory sustainability research and problem solving. This capacity includes advanced skills in communicating, deliberating and negotiating, collaborating, leadership, pluralistic and trans-cultural thinking, and empathy. All of these skills are particularly important for successful stakeholder collaboration and a necessity for the majority of methods assigned to previous competencies.	Collaborative, participatory, interdisciplinary, civic competence

These five competences comprise knowledge and set of basic skills, namely interdisciplinary knowledge, critical thinking, communication, creative thinking, problem solving, collaboration, which overlap with some of competences listed in *Table 1*.

4 CONCLUSION

From the literature review, two major opportunities to combine sustainability and Industry 4.0 emerge, at technological and at competence levels.

At a technological level, Industry 4.0 enables to integrate sustainability strategies throughout the entire supply chain, allowing a more efficient use of resources (e.g. less use of raw materials, lower energy consumption, less waste and reduced greenhouse gas emissions) and energy. However, sustainability strategies need to be integrated and become explicitly part of the company's business model.

At a competence level, whereas there is an overlap of competences needed for Sustainability and Industry 4.0, especially transversal competences such as problem solving, communication, creativity, leadership, collaboration, lifelong learning (see *Table 1* and *Table 2*). Even though emphasis is given to competences, knowledge is also common to both (see for example, normative knowledge in sustainability competence framework and domain knowledge in Industry 4.0 competence framework). In addition, new competences emerge from Industry 4.0 such as the digital skills. If in the past, digital skills were more associated to specific areas of engineering, for the future they are seen as generic whereas all employees should master them.

Furthermore, competences that seem to be exclusive of Industry 4.0 and Sustainability might also be seen as transversal. For example, digital skills are closely used to technologies, which will be embedded in the future work place, such as automation and IoT. Considering that, it is through the Industry 4.0 technologies that companies can become more sustainable, digital skills also become relevant for sustainability problem solving. On the other hand, anticipatory competence might be relevant in Industry 4.0 context, whereas technological trends, customer's needs and expectations might be anticipated.

Engineering education research community already have an awareness for change and curriculum innovation needed to cope with Industry 4.0, the competence profiles and sustainability crises however, they remain disarticulated and detached. Literature shows examples of curriculum change to integrate sustainability, [18] as an example, and to innovate engineering curriculum to address the companies' needs [4][19], as examples. These point out the type of curriculum and learning environment suitable to address both Sustainability challenges and Industry 4.0 demands, namely a more flexible curriculum, active and student-centred, focus on process rather than in the product, such as Problem, Project Based Learning (PBL).

Nevertheless, literature does not address Sustainability and Industry 4.0 combined. Consequently, the challenge for engineering education is to reflect in their role, foster curriculum change and innovation, and integrate adequately sustainability and Industry 4.0 as part of engineering qualification profile. What and how to educate engineers for Industry 4.0 and Sustainability are examples of questions that need empirical research and in collaboration with several stakeholders, namely other engineering education institutions and companies from private and public sectors.

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